

MENSTRUATION, DIGNITY, AND JUSTICE: RECOGNISING MENSTRUAL HYGIENE AS A FUNDAMENTAL HUMAN RIGHT IN ZILLA PARISHAD SCHOOL

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Abstract

Environmental Justice and Human Rights must be equal for every individual globally, free from discrimination based on caste, sex, religion, or any other ground. The foundation of human rights in the Republic of India is enshrined in ⁶Article 21 of the Constitution, which states that 'No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by law.' The objective of the study is to find the menstrual hygiene management practices in Zilla Parishad Schools and to check the awareness about Menstruation and Human Rights in Zilla Parishad Schools. The methodology for this will be well well-structured Questionnaire and in-person interviews of Stakeholders of Zilla Parishad schools, and a literature survey on research work on a similar line. The various Zilla Parishad schools of Thane District: Urban, Semi-Urban and Rural areas had been selected for conducting the research. The research will be conducted through various visits and interactions with stakeholders to identify various methods for Menstrual Hygiene practices for school girls. The study will reveal the Factual data and the practices performed in the Zilla Parishad Schools. The purpose of this study is to show how poor menstrual hygiene management can lead to violations of Human rights. The findings of this study tell us that there is a lack of Menstrual Hygiene management and which subsequently violates human rights. To overcome this, the Zilla Parishad Schools and Rural Schools should mandatorily install Sanitary Napkin Vending Machines and Disposal Mechanisms like Incinerators or Covered Bins in every girls' washroom of ZP Schools. The keywords of this study are Environment, Human Rights, Clean Environment, Menstrual Hygiene, Menstruation, Menstrual Hygiene Management, Menstrual Products, Zilla Parishad (ZP) Schools.

INTRODUCTION:

Menstruation, a natural process that is required for the development of every woman's body. In modern times, the word 'MENSTRUATION' is still taboo, shameful, silent, and neglected by Society. Many of them cannot understand that it is a natural biological process. Due to a lack of Menstrual Hygiene Management in the schools, many of the school girls are not only affecting their health but also their Fundamental Rights like the Right to education, the Right to dignity, the Right to equality, and the Right to a clean Environment. Identifying Menstrual Hygiene as a Fundamental Human Right because due to poor Menstrual Hygiene Management [MHM], there would be a lead in absenteeism, infections, and feelings of shame, ultimately violating their Right to education and Right to equality. So to check the awareness of Menstruation, my mother and my colleague visited the various Zilla Parishad Schools of Thane District. So the findings of this study will be based on the information from Zilla Parishad Schools. In recent times in India, many schemes are implemented by the ⁹Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, like **Menstrual Hygiene Scheme (MHS)**,⁷**Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP)**, ⁸**Rashtriya Kishor Swasthya Karyakram (RKSK)**, **Jan Aushadhi Suvidha (JAS)** and many state schemes like ⁵ **KHUSI** program in Odisha, ³**ASMITA YOJANA** in Maharashtra and many more. Implementation of the Scheme is not only the task; proper functioning is the core objective of it. After visiting the Zilla Parishad Schools, many of the school girls are unaware of the word menstruation, and the conditions of the Washrooms in the School are worse, with no proper cleanliness, and many of the girls who have started their Menstrual Cycle remain absent in school and are afraid how they can ask a Male Faculty member about this.

The research was conducted and came to know that many of the girls who had started their Menstrual cycle are still using the Cloth, and using the cloth on those days can cause infections, cancer and even death can happen. Also showed them and distributed the menstrual products like Sanitary napkins, Menstrual cup, Tampons, etc. This shows we are still in the era of the 90s. Overall, from this, we clearly state that it is a complete violation of basic fundamental Human rights. Apart from this, we are always spreading awareness to girls about the Menstrual Cycle in schools, colleges and universities, but instead we should also spread to Boys, if they also get the knowledge about what the Menstrual Cycle is. In future, they can definitely help if someone wants help, and it will have a better impact on society at large. This will boost the confidence of every woman on the planet.

OBJECTIVES:

The study, “Menstruation, Dignity, and Justice: Recognising Menstrual Hygiene as a Fundamental Human Right”, aims to check the awareness of Menstrual Hygiene in Zilla Parishad (ZP) Schools. The objectives of the study are laid out as follows :

1. To check the awareness and knowledge about Menstrual Hygiene in Zilla Parishad (ZP) Schools
2. To check the Environmental Conditions
3. To establish the link between the Menstrual Hygiene and Fundamental Human Rights

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

The methodology for this study is as follows:

1. Primary Data Collection: The study focuses on how Menstrual Hygiene is interlinked with Fundamental Human Rights. It focuses on Primary Data [collected from Zilla Parishad (ZP) Schools] and on a deep analysis of the concept of Menstruation. The area for this research is selected Zilla Parishad schools of Thane District: Urban, Semi-Urban and Rural areas. School-going students aged 10-14 years were selected for the study, irrespective of gender. Considering these factors, a well-structured questionnaire was prepared, and in-person interviews with various Stakeholders of Zilla Parishad schools were conducted.
2. Secondary Data Collection: A literature survey on previous studies and research work on a similar line was studied thoroughly to avoid research gaps in the current research. The study also provided the scenario and the condition of menstrual hygiene in various parts of India.

OBSERVATIONS :

The following are the images of Zilla Parishad Schools :

Image 1

Image 2

Observations after visiting the Zilla Parishad Schools :

- 1) The Cleanliness in the surroundings of Zilla Parishad (ZP) should be more required to prevent diseases and infections.
- 2) The need for more washrooms in Zilla Parishad (ZP) schools, as the number of students is higher.
- 3) There should be proper installation of Sanitary Napkins/Pads Vending Machine and disposal mechanisms like Incinerators or Covered Bins in every girls' washroom of ZP Schools.
- 4) When the discussions were started with the students, we came to know that, yes, there is a lack of awareness about menstrual hygiene and fundamental human rights.
- 5) Some of the girls said that they still used the CLOTH during the Menstrual Cycle, which can cause infection, and in cases, death is also possible.

So, these are the independent observations at Zilla Parishad (ZP) Schools.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS :

The result of the study is as follows :

1. Do you think access to a clean and pollution-free...

2. Have you faced or observed social stigma regarding...

3. Do you believe menstrual hygiene is linked to dignity and...

4. Are improvements needed in schools to support Menstrual...

5. Are menstrual hygiene products (sanitary napkins, menstrual cups, tampon etc) easily accessible and...

6. Do you think every citizen, regardless of caste, gender, or economic status, enjoys equal dignity ?

7. Do you believe that a polluted environment violates human dignity ?

8. Would you participate in awareness campaigns on Menstrual Hygiene or Clean Environment ?

9. What factors do you believe most undermine human dignity in india ?

10. During the menstrual cycle, what you use cloth or sanitary napkins or other products?

From the above results, the discussions came forward that a clean and pollution-free environment is mandatory for various reasons. Menstrual hygiene is one of the reasons for this study, and it shows how it is directly linked with human dignity and followed by fundamental human rights. It also highlights that in the modern world, the word 'MENSTRUATION' is still a social stigma. The fact that many of the school-going girls still use cloth instead of menstrual products like sanitary napkins/pads, tampons, menstrual cups, etc. Lack of Health care and Sanitation are the factors that undermine human dignity the most, and it shows that every citizen, regardless of caste, gender, or economic does not enjoy equal rights.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY :

A] Scopes of the study :

- The Study focuses on identifying the awareness of Menstrual Hygiene and Menstrual Hygiene Management, which directly or indirectly relates to Fundamental Rights.
- It highlights the socio-cultural taboos in society.
- It also shows the practical awareness of the Menstrual Products like Sanitary Napkins, Tampons, Menstrual cup, etc and their distribution.
- The study also included the responses of Male Teachers and Female Teachers, and Students (both boys and girls).

B] Limitations of the study :

- The research is limited to selected Zilla Parishad Schools within the Thane district, whether Urban, Semi-urban, or Rural area.
- Some Girls and boys are not comfortable with the topic, so we could not collect more data.
- There was a time barrier due to festivals, so I couldn't visit more schools.

CONCLUSIONS/RECOMMENDATIONS :

So after the findings of this study :

1. We should be free to say the word 'MENSTRUATION'
2. Educate and spread awareness irrespective of gender.
3. Every Zilla Parishad School should have a Sanitary Napkin Vending machine and Disposal Mechanisms like Incinerators or Covered Bins in every girls' washroom of ZP Schools.
4. There should be more mass media awareness programs on Menstruation and menstrual Hygiene.

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